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OXIDATIVE STRESS AND MUSCLE CELL DAMAGE BIOMARKERS MONITORING IN MALE VOLLEYBALL ATHLETES DURING A COMPETITIVE SEASON

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ABSTRACT

Neto, J.M.F.A.; Nader B.B.; Ornellas, T.C.F.; Siviero, I.M.P.S.; Padovani, R.M. Oxidative stress and muscle cell damage biomarkers monitoring in male volleyball athletes during a competitive season. *Brazilian Journal of Biomotricity*. v. 7, n. 4, p. 208-218, 2013. This study evaluated the oxidative stress markers in volleyball players along three distinct phases of a championship to determine if they were able to reflect the different stress levels (phase 1: low intensity exercises; phase 2: increase in load of training and start of the championship; phase 3: decreases in sessions and load of training and the final phase of the championship). We measured the antioxidant status (catalase-CAT, glutathione reductase-GR activities and plasma total sulfhydryl groups-TSG concentration); the oxidant status (reactive carbonyl derivatives-RCD and thiobarbituric acid reactive substances-TBARS concentrations); and assessed the muscular damage levels through plasma creatine kinase (CK) activity in blood samples of non-trained subjects (n = 9) and volleyball players (n = 9). We found at phase 2 a significant increase of plasma RCD concentration and an evident tendency of increase in plasma CK activity. At this moment, the antioxidant enzyme activities decreased to the lowest levels. The decrease in overload during phase 3 induced a significant up-regulation of enzyme activities and an important decrease of RCD in comparison with phase 2. The biomarkers analyzed reflected the different degree of stress imposed during the championship and showed that the players presented the lowest oxidative stress level combined with the best performance parameters during the principal phase (phase 3) of the championship.

Key-words: antioxidant enzymes, creatine kinase, oxidative stress, plyometric exercise, volleyball training.

INTRODUCTION

Volleyball is a sport that requires mainly explosive resistance training to create specific increases in muscle activation and force development. Improved motor performance, specifically significant increases in the vertical jump may be obtained by plyometric training (LEES, GRAHAM-SMITH, 1996). This kind of exercises employs a quick, powerful movement involving a pre-stretch of the muscle (eccentric contraction) followed by a shortening concentric muscular contraction, using the stretch-shortening muscular cycle (BOSCO et al., 1982; CLARKSON et al., 1992). However, the plyometric training seems to potentially cause more muscle damage than conventional high intensity exercise (LIEBER et al., 1996).

Considering that the volleyball training requires exhausting loads of plyometric exercises and eccentric contractions, there is a large possibility that the mechanical stress could trigger a secondary inflammatory process, with an elevated infiltration of inflammatory cells (BEATON et al., 2002; HELLSTEN et al., 1997); this would increase the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and potentially raise the post-exercise propagation of muscle damage (FIELDING et al., 2000; JAESCHKE, 1995; TIIDUS, 1998). When the generation of ROS exceeds the ability of the antioxidant systems, the resultant oxidative stress can cause muscle damage (ALESSIO, GOLDFARB, 1988; JAESCKE, 1995; RADÁK et al., 1999). Ji (2002) stated that the best strategy to enhance endogenous antioxidant levels is the oxidative stress itself, proposing that sub maximal increases in ROS production induced by training may increase the tolerance to higher exercise loads, reinforcing the hypothesis that exercise intensity modulates antioxidant defense capacity (ALESSIO, GOLDFARB, 1988; BEJMA, JI, 2002; JI, 2002; REID, 2001; SEN, 1995; SMOLKA et al., 2000).

To date, there is not consistent evidence supporting reliable blood markers, which would be representative to indicate training-induced redox status alterations and its relationship with performance in volleyball players. In one isolated study, it was reported altered blood redox markers status in female volleyball players after pre-competitive phase of the training schedule (MARTINOVIC et al., 2011). However, a time course of these parameters throughout the entire process, including the competitive phase, was not made. Thus, our purpose was to verify the impact produced by different moments of effort intensity with different levels of plyometric exercise loads during an entire training season upon blood redox status markers and its relationship with muscle damage markers. In addition, we also want to verify if the chosen blood biomarkers were suitable to detect the degree of impact.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Subjects

Nine male, volleyball players of competitive level, aged 17.88 ± 1.05 yr, body mass 81.15 ± 8.73 Kg and height 189.27 ± 6.33 cm (mean \pm SD) were monitored along the principal competition of this category. The control group was formed by nine male, aged 18.7 ± 1.76 yr, body mass 73.4 ± 5.76 Kg and height 175.32 ± 4.76 cm (mean \pm SD), not engaged in athletic training and exhaustive exercises. All subjects were fully informed of the risks and stress associated with the project and signed a consenting document, with was approved by the local Ethics Committee.

Analysis

We analyzed the oxidative stress biomarkers and applied the physical performance tests at three different moments: one at the pre-competitive (phase 1) and two at the competitive (phases 2 and 3) periods. Each phase was planned with different weight training loads and kinds of plyometric and weight exercises, according to the concept of "complex training" proposed by Chu (1996).

Phase 1: pre-competitive (5 weeks)

It was used high-volume, low-intensity weight training (3 sets of 20 repetitions of 60% one-repetition maximum – 60% 1RM, 4 times on the week) and low to moderate intensity plyometric

exercises (technical and coordination exercises, 3 times on the week). This phase coincides also with classification phase of the championship.

Phase 2: competitive I (5 weeks)

The weight training consisted of 4 sets of 10 repetitions of 80% 1RM (4 times on the week). The plyometrics included depth jumps, which started with 60-foot contacts from a 25-inch box (first week) until 150 foot contacts from boxes varying 30 to 55 inches (3 times on the subsequent weeks). This phase corresponds to play-off of the championship.

Phase 3: competitive II (3 weeks)

The load of weight training returned to 60% 1RM (2 times on the week) and the plyometrics were maintained using exercises of low to moderate intensity (technical and coordination exercises) with a maximum of 150 foot contacts during a session (2 times on the week).

Procedures

All biochemical analysis were made in the last week of each phase, with an interval of 48 hours after the last session of exhaustive exercises. The first test of physical performance (vertical jump using a free countermovement and bench press) occurred in the pre-season, 3 months before the beginning of phase 1. The second and third tests of physical performance coincided with the moments of the second (phase 2) and third (phase 3) biochemical analysis to establish a relationship between the results of the physical performance tests and the values of the oxidative stress biomarkers at these same moments.

Plasma samples and the preparation of hemolysate

Blood samples were collected from the hepatic vein using heparinized syringes. The plasma was separated from blood cells by centrifugation at 1,000 g for 10 min and then transferred to a fresh tube, and stored at -80°C until analysis. The red blood cells were lysed with double distilled water (1:1, v/v) and stored at -80°C until the determination of catalase (CAT) and glutathione reductase (GR) activities. The concentration of Hb was determined by the Drabkin method.

Enzyme assays

The hemolysate was diluted 1:20 in 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0, before assaying. All enzyme assays were done in triplicate using the following methods. Catalase (EC 1.11.1.6) activity was measured in 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) by monitoring the decrease in absorbance at 240 nm for 30 s after the addition of 10 mM hydrogen peroxide (AEBI, 1984). The erythrocyte CAT activity was expressed as k.gHb-1.min-1. The GR (EC 1.6.4.2) activity was measured in 0.2 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) containing 2 mM EDTA, 0.1 mM NADPH and 0.75 mM DTNB (5,5'-dithio-bis(2-nitrobenzoic acid)). GSSG (1 mM) was added to the cuvette to start the reaction and the absorbance was followed at 412 nm for 3 min (SMITH et al., 1988). The erythrocyte GR activity was expressed as IU.gHb-1.min-1.

Plasma total sulphhydryl groups

The plasma total sulphhydryl groups (TSG) were estimated according to Faure and Lafond (FAURE, LAFOND, 1995). The concentration of plasma total sulphhydryl groups was expressed in $\mu\text{mol.L}^{-1}$.

Plasma reactive carbonyl derivatives

The plasma reactive carbonyl derivatives (RCD) were determined spectrophotometrically by reaction with the classic carbonyl reagent 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNPH) (FAURE, LAFOND, 1995).

Thiobarbituric acid reactive substances

The extension of lipid peroxidation was determined by the reaction of thiobarbituric acid (TBA) with malondialdehyde (MDA), a product formed by lipid peroxidation. The plasma TBARS levels were determined fluorometrically, according to Yagi (1987).

Statistical analysis

The data are expressed as the means \pm standard deviation (SD), indicated by vertical bars in the Figures. A one-way analysis of variance was employed and Turkey pos-hoc analysis was used to locate the differences. The program "Statistics for Windows", version 4.3 (Statsoft, Inc. 1993) was used for statistical analysis using $P < 0.05$ as the confidence limit.

RESULTS

Antioxidant Status

Figure 1 shows the erythrocyte CAT (A) and GR (B) activities and plasma TSG (C) as markers of the antioxidant status, obtained at the three training phases. In comparison with the control group, GR ($8,9 \pm 0,7$ IU.gHb⁻¹.min⁻¹) and CAT ($0,37 \pm 0,03$ k.gHb⁻¹.min⁻¹) activities showed a different pattern of response with GR activity significantly higher in all three phases (phase 1: $12,7 \pm 0,5$ IU.gHb⁻¹.min⁻¹; phase 2: $11,9 \pm 0,3$ IU.gHb⁻¹.min⁻¹; phase 3: $13,2 \pm 0,3$ IU.gHb⁻¹.min⁻¹) analyzed while CAT activity has not been significantly affected during the different phases (phase 1: $0,359 \pm 0,02$ k.gHb⁻¹.min⁻¹; phase 2: $0,325 \pm 0,04$ k.gHb⁻¹.min⁻¹; phase 3: $0,382 \pm 0,04$ k.gHb⁻¹.min⁻¹). On the other hand, we found significant differences ($P < 0.05$) of CAT and GR activities in phase 3 in comparison with phase 2. No significant differences in TSG (C) concentration during all phases analyzed were observed (control: 499 ± 35 μ mol.L⁻¹; phase 1: 510 ± 40 μ mol.L⁻¹; phase 2: 520 ± 40 μ mol.L⁻¹; phase 3: 505 ± 35 μ mol.L⁻¹).

Figure 1. Erythrocyte CAT (A) and GR (B) activities and plasma TSG (C) of the control group and volleyball players at three phases of training and competition. Data are means \pm SD ($n = 9$). * $P < 0.05$ compared with phase 2; ** $P < 0.05$ compared with control; # $P < 0.001$ compared with control and $P < 0.05$ compared with phase 2.

Oxidative Stress Biomarkers

Plasma RCD (A) and TBARS (B) concentrations at the three moments of analysis were taken as markers of oxidative attack in proteins and lipids, respectively, and are presented in Figure 2. RCD showed a significant increase at phase 2 ($160 \pm 40 \mu\text{mol.L}^{-1}$) in comparison with both the control group ($88 \pm 15 \mu\text{mol.L}^{-1}$; $P < 0.001$) and phase 1 ($122 \pm 17 \mu\text{mol.L}^{-1}$; $P < 0.05$). The increase observed at phase 2 was followed by a significant decrease, near to the control value at phase 3 ($80 \pm 22 \mu\text{mol.L}^{-1}$; $P < 0.001$). No significant differences in plasma TBARS concentrations were observed (control: $1,12 \pm 0,08 \text{ nmol.L}^{-1}$; phase 1: $1,15 \pm 0,09 \text{ nmol.L}^{-1}$; phase 2: $1,25 \pm 0,15 \text{ nmol.L}^{-1}$; phase 3: $1,27 \pm 0,17 \text{ nmol.L}^{-1}$).

Figure 2. Plasma RCD (A) and TBARS (B) concentrations of the control group and volleyball players at three phases of training and competition. Data are means \pm SD ($n = 9$). * $P < 0.001$ compared with control and $P < 0.05$ compared with phase 1; ** $P < 0.001$ compared with phase 2.

Muscle Damage Alterations

Figure 3 shows the plasma CK concentration under the same conditions described before. We found significant increase in plasma CK level ($P < 0.001$) between the three phases (phase 1: 200 ± 50 U.L⁻¹; phase 2: 260 ± 70 U.L⁻¹; phase 3: 220 ± 80 U.L⁻¹) and the control group (68 ± 20 U.L⁻¹). We found also a tendency of increase of plasma CK level mainly in phase 2 compared to phases 1 and 3.

Figure 3. Plasma creatine kinase (CK) activity of the control group and volleyball players at three phases of training and competition. Data are means \pm SD ($n = 9$). * $P < 0.001$ compared with control.

Physical Performance Parameters

Figure 4 shows the results from vertical jump (A) and bench press (B) tests at the three different moments described before. The vertical jump test showed a significant increase at two moments of

the training (phase 2: 66 ± 5 cm; phase 3: 72 ± 5 cm) in comparison with the test done at the pre-season (55 ± 4 cm): at phase 2 ($P<0.01$) and at phase 3 ($P<0.001$). Similarly to the vertical jump test, the bench press test showed a progressive increase of maximal strength of superior members, but no significant statistical differences were obtained for this parameter (pre-season: 65 ± 17 Kg; phase 2: 77 ± 15 Kg; phase 3: 80 ± 12 Kg).

Figure 4. Vertical jump (A) and bench press (B) tests at the three different moments of the training and competition. The performance tests were executed only with athletes. Data are means \pm SD ($n = 9$). * $P<0.01$ compared with pre-season. ** $P<0.001$ compared with pre-season.

DISCUSSION

The main contribution of the present investigation was to show that the biochemical markers analyzed here were efficient to indicate the different oxidative stress level reached during a competitive season, specifically in male volleyball players. Phase 2 represented the moment where the training and competitions were more intense, with a program of heavy plyometric exercises together with stressful and difficult games, as it was the classification phase. We found lower

erythrocyte antioxidant enzymes activities associated with higher plasma RCD concentration at this phase compared to the other phases. Plasma CK activity was higher in this phase as well, probably reflecting a higher muscular stress imposed by the high-intensity training at that moment. These overload increase could be a factor to induce a transitory down-regulation of the enzyme activities.

Radák and colleagues (1999) also observed an increase in RCD level of skeletal muscle proteins followed by a decrease of the antioxidant defense system after training. It is possible that ROS generated from activated alveolar macrophages during anaerobic exercise are involved not only in the inflammation process (GOTO et al., 1999) but also in protein oxidation (HALLIWELL, 1988). The rise in RCD appears to be related to muscle production of an intermediate resembling the hydroxyl radical (LEEWENBURGH et al., 1999). It was also suggested that specific cellular proteins are more susceptible to oxidative modifications than others, specially the contractile proteins (GOTO et al., 1999; RADÁK et al., 1997). The plasma TSG of biological molecules, proceeding mainly from proteins and the reduced form of glutathione (GSH) are important targets for free radicals attack and decreased concentration may indicate high oxidative attack level (FAURE, LAFOND, 1995).

Contrary to the observed for protein oxidation, the extent of plasma lipid peroxidation did not differ during the different moments analyzed. Miyazaki and collaborators (2001) observed that the up-regulation in erythrocyte antioxidant enzyme activities might reduce the exercise-induced lipid peroxidation. The training-induced increase in GR activity observed in our study may represent an adaptation sufficient to prevent enhanced lipid peroxidation despite training had no effect on the CAT activity compared to control values. These differential training responses of antioxidant enzymes were expected because most studies have shown that exercise does not exert a uniform effect on all antioxidants (KIM et al., 1996; MIYAZAKI et al., 2001; ORTENBLAD et al., 1999; PACKER, 1997). Furthermore, erythrocyte GR activity was significantly higher during all analysis in the athletes compared to the control subjects, possibly reflecting the exercise-induced oxidative stress as an important signal in stimulating the antioxidant systems via activation of redox-sensitive signaling pathways (REID, 2001).

Our biomarkers were also able to reflect the lightest exercise intensity planned for the last period before the final games (phase 3). At this moment the antioxidant activity was higher and the RCD level was lower than at phase 2, suggesting that a training modulation through the reduction of the volume and intensity of the high-intensity exercises during phase 3 was efficient to up-regulate again the antioxidant enzyme activities, contributing to decrease the RCD level. The physical tests measured in this work correlated with the good performance of the team during the play-off games (phase 3) of the championship (Figure 4). Despite the decrease of antioxidant status and an elevation of RCD level during phase 2, the adaptive potential of the players at that moment was more vigorous than the stressful stimulus as shown through plasma CK activity, TSG and TBARS concentrations, permitting a progressive acquisition in physical performance (Figure 4). A possible explanation for this finding is that the oxidative stress generated during phase 2 did not reach a threshold of cellular redox state after that the performance falls as proposed by others (REID, 2001).

In conclusion, the biomarkers analyzed during the championship reflected the different degree of stress imposed and showed also that the athletes presented the lowest oxidative stress level combined with the best performance parameters during the principal phase (phase 3) of the championship.

PRACTICAL APPLICATIONS

Evidently, using only oxidative stress markers will not be enough to prevent injuries or still overreaching/overtraining in volleyball players. Because of the complex processes involved with the establishment of these conditions, other variables must be evaluated to make a more complete diagnosis, as indicated by additional current research from the present group (ANTUNES NETO et al., 2006; LAZARIM et al., 2009; SMITH et al., 1988; ZOPPI, MACEDO, 2008). However, the

possibility of using oxidative stress analysis as a practical alternative for the early detection of fatigue or muscle overloading in volleyball players exposes an inexpensive alternative pathway to physically preserve the players and improve the management of effort load and recovery period even during a championship. This may contribute to optimal physical conditioning, combining individual stress limits and muscle protection for all athletes. Our results also suggest the possibility of using plasma CK activity analysis as a marker for the early detection of fatigue or muscle overload in volleyball players. Determining an upper limit for CK activity and comparing players CK against a reference value may contribute not only to protecting them physically but also to optimizing their training schedule.

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